

**A STUDY OF CORRELATION BETWEEN ROLE EFFICACY AND
TEACHER ORIENTATION OF SECONDARY
SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Introduction

The performance of a person working in an organization depends on his own potential effectiveness as a person, his technical competence, his managerial experience as well as the way the role which he performs in organization is designed. It is the integration of two ensures the person's effectiveness in the organization.

Unless the person has the required for the role, he cannot be effective, but equally importance is how the role which he occupies in the organization is designed. If the role does not allow him to use his competence and he constantly feels frustrated in the role, his effectiveness is likely to be low. The integration of the person and the role comes when the role is able to fulfil the need of individual. Teacher role efficacy can be seen as the psychological effectiveness of a role.

Teacher with a high level of student orientation gives more importance to the development of knowledge and skills amongst student. A teacher with a high level of content orientation gives more importance to teaching the content matter to student rather than the all round development of students.

Such as teacher has desire to acquire latest knowledge in the subject matter, update the learning material used by him/her, make effort for his/her own professional development, makes detailed plan of each classroom activity, implements new teaching approaches in class room, desire to be known as an effective teacher, teachers basic as well progressive curricula, emphasizes systematic student evaluation and attends professional meeting such a teachers focus is to reach content

matter to the student teacher role efficacy and teacher orientation of secondary school teachers

Review of related literature

A review of related literature the necessary insight in to the problem widens the knowledge of the researcher and ensures the avoidance of unnecessary duplication it also helps the researcher to decide her methodology tools sample and technique analysis.

Rawal H. (2002) studied the relation between emotional intelligence and teacher efficacy of high school teachers. Kasare A. (2005) studied the relation between concept of teacher's efficacy perception and emotional intelligence Patel (1999) conducted a study on teacher's orientation in relation to teacher personality, teacher beliefs and teaching experience Mallika, M (1991) A study of role conflict perception by ited of school and its relationship to role efficacy teacher role efficacy and teacher orientation variables are not studied more so this topics ha been selected for research.

Need of the Study

review of related literature shows that researches on teacher role efficacy out looks of student towards teaching participation in job social and population faction teachers effectiveness and efficacy organizational climate and leadership regarding college and university teacher primary teachers temporary teacher as well as studies has been conducted but teacher role efficacy related to their teacher orientation student orientation variables are not studied much so researcher decided to study this variable at high school level and to study the correlation between them this is descriptive study for correlation between them. This is descriptive study for correlation between teacher role efficacy and teacher orientation had been studied.

Statement of problems

A study of correlation between role efficacy and teacher orientation of secondary school teachers

Aim of the study

To study conducted the following broad aim:

To study of secondary school teachers in relation to the following variables:

1) Teachers role efficacy

2) Teacher orientation

Objective of the Study

1) To study of correlation between role efficacy and teacher orientation of secondary school teachers

2) To study of correlation between role efficacy and teacher orientation of female secondary school teacher

3) To study of correlation between role efficacy and teacher orientation of male secondary school teacher

Hypotheses of the study

1) There is no significant correlation between the teacher orientations

2) There is no significant correlation between secondary school teachers role efficacy and teachers orientation

3) There is no significant correlation between the male secondary school teachers

Definitions of Terms

1) Role efficacy: It refers to a teacher's conviction of confidence about his other abilities to mobilize the motivation cognitive resource and course of action need to successfully perform the role of teachers in his or her school.

2) Teacher orientation: it refers to the extent to which the teacher places emphasis on facilitating student's psychological, social, emotional and intellectual growth and development.

Scope and delimitation of the study

For present research study Thane district is selected. Under the Thane district These Taluka's are selected Viz ,Kalyan , Ulhasnagar and Ambarnath other Taluka's are excluded under this research study forty three secondary school of Marathi mediums the Thane district are select included in this study while pre-primary, primary, higher secondary school and college is teachers are not included in this study . All teachers are graduate and completed B.Ed. The drawing teacher, D.Ed. teacher, Music Teacher and Physical instruction are not included in this research.

Methodology

The researcher has used the descriptive method of correlation and the study was conducted in casual comparative type has been implemented.

Sample

For the purpose of the present research a representative sample of 350 secondary school teachers was selected from 43 secondary school schools has selected in private aided and private unaided 173 female teacher and 177 male teachers selected from these schools using sample random sampling technique

Tools of the Study

The researcher used opinion to collect data for the present study. Spires' inventory for teacher orientation and role efficacy scale of udayrari (1987) for teacher role efficacy

Analysis of Data

In the present study the descriptive analysis of data was done in terms of mean and standard deviation. The inferential analysis was done using person's coefficient of correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Hypotheses of the study

There is no significant correlation between secondary school teachers role efficacy and teachers orientation.

Table

Correlation between Role Efficacy and Teacher

Orientation of Secondary School Teachers

Group	Sample	Df	Table 'r'		Coefficient of correlation	Level of significant
			0.05	0.01		
Female	173	171	0.152	0.197	0.0438	No Significant
Male	177	175	0.149	0.195	0.0291	
Total Teacher	350	348	0.106	0.137	0.0351	

Interpretation

While studying the correlation among female, male and total teacher of secondary school teacher role efficacy and Teacher orientation value of 'r' is less than the value in the table 'r' so this hypothesis is accepted on the 0.05 level of significance.

Conclusion

There is no significant correlation female, male and total teacher of secondary school teachers among the role efficacy and teacher orientation.

Significance of the study

This research work will help for self-awareness and self-motivation of teachers. It will analysis the strength, weakness, opportunity and threats in teachers role efficacy of teachers. It will useful to principle for better school management and find the weakness of the college teachers and to give guidance and help for the development of school teachers.

Reference

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